

METHODOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF USING FOLKLORE IN EXTRACURRICULAR READING CLASSES.

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Introduction:

One of the reasons why the genre of fairy tales is well received by children in folklore, they are interesting and read into images is the impressiveness, educativeness of the language of fairy tales, the appreciation of friendly relations, the constant victory over evil, sharpness, meaningfulness and is closeness to the vernacular. Most of the folktales, proverbs, narratives, short stories, and stories are combined with real life images and short characters taken from past events. The sharp, interesting plot of the folklore, the extraordinary and wonderful situation in the story will fascinate children, the brave, strong, intelligent, resourceful, brave, brave and agile heroes in them, the ideological direction of the fairy tale, goodness, the power of goodness in it. The fact that he always wins attracts children. The form of reception described in the fairy tale is very interesting for children, the repetition of the same words and phrases, the melodiousness, the expressiveness of the language, the vividness of the means of expression. The participants in the fairy tale are often the personification of the kind, generous, fair, and their opposite, evil, miserly, and greedy. The value of the teacher in the fairy tale is that the children are happy that the rightness and honesty won in him, that the poor people were saved from difficulties, that is, that goodness and goodness came true, and that evil and evil were condemned. They want and believe that it will always be like this in life. If a child believes and is interested in fairy tales, his outlook, thinking, and knowledge will increase. For example, in the fairy tale "Honesty" the main idea is to help the poor, to live by their own work, and the idea that this is even the desire of the whole nation is put forward, while in the fairy tale "The Punishment of the Trickster" The idea that the slyness will win over the scheming of the swindler and that betrayal will not go unpunished is put forward. Both tales end with the victory of the right word. Such a victory is expressed in magical tales in addition to household tales. The fairy tale instills in children the belief that good will always win, while discussing the behavior of the heroes and developing the ability to evaluate them. Children in the process of analyzing the fairy tale "What qualities did you like in people? (or didn't like?)", "why?" "... Why was he punished?" (or encouraged)" , "Why are some characters in fairy tales supported even by the forces of nature? (or will he turn his back on some?)" in the process of finding answers, they observe, discuss and come to a conclusion. Tales about animals are read more often in preschools and elementary schools. Tales such as

"The Tale of the Wolf as a Doctor" (Anvar Obidjon), "The Fox with the Pot" are read and analyzed based on imagery in the style of a real life story.

When reading fairy tales, they should be read according to the character of each animal. It is very important for the teacher to enter the role of each character. But it is not recommended to compare such tales to the character of people. In addition to reflecting the general aspects of education, examples of Uzbek folk art also confirm and encourage goodness, goodness and humanity in beautiful, instructive examples.

Since schoolchildren, especially 2nd-3rd graders, have acquired reading skills at a certain level, it is necessary to pay more attention to independent work on texts, fairy tales, stories, poems, narratives. It is necessary for students to be able to choose convenient methods and to approach work creatively in order to complete the task quickly and correctly. Pupils do not learn such things by themselves, of course, such knowledge, skills and abilities are acquired by the teacher in separate classes. Only when working under the guidance of a teacher, they learned to think, creatively perform practical exercises, find mistakes and correct them.

It is known that fairy tales embody didactic and instructive tools. The feature of predictability of created-fictional events in them is instructive. The fairy tales that have been refined over the centuries and have come down to us with their deep and deep content are among the most beloved and most attractive examples of folk art. The artistic power of fairy tales is that they reflect people's spirit, together with their hopes and dreams and the realities of life, for both adults and children. It is also pleasant and interesting. The educational importance of fairy tales is that they express the four seasons of the year, natural phenomena, people's feelings, inner experiences, and even their actions. As the child grows up, his worldview, thinking, attention to the environment, memory and concepts develop. The outside world expands and shines before his eyes. Children begin to understand human images more clearly and clearly. Little by little, children develop ideas about liars, tricksters, good-natured, fair, conscientious, compassionate, compassionate people. The children who deeply felt this are life events, the image of a person is depicted in a legend - Ur weaving, - open table, - flying carpet, - hot khumcha, - Peasant and bear, - fairy tales like emerald and expensive, - Cat with crow, - Fables such as the lying shepherd are considered an important tool in raising children to be good people and growing up as individuals. Zumrad and expensive fairy tale is mainly reflected in the actions of good moral character of Emerald, and bad moral character of Kimmatt. Because Zumrad is polite, polite, humble and hardworking, even the sorceress is loved and respected. He made his father happy with the wealth he gave. Father and son lived happily ever after. Nature honored him in her arms. Due to his impoliteness, rudeness, lack of interest, laziness, stubbornness and ruthlessness, disrespect for adults, the sorcerer was angry with the old woman. If modern education and the ideology of independence is nourished by this heritage, if it accepts its best pages and rules, it can honorably fulfill the goals and tasks it has set for itself.

Children try to be like the heroes of fairy tales, they want to have magical things, or they dream of becoming a magician and having unlimited power like the hero. With the help of a fairy tale, they travel in the deserts of good and evil, in the hills and mountains. From such a period, they begin to understand what is good and what is bad. As children grow up, they tell stories to their younger ones, encourage them to be smart, restrained, to stop being stubborn and capricious. They also behave as small educators. In general, folk art is a complex of

wisdom for young and old alike. Even though the centuries pass and educational issues are artistically expressed in the works of our great scholars, the folklore works, which are the product of the people's thinking, continue to gain worldwide significance from a spiritual point of view. It takes a lot of time to teach the above features to elementary school students. There is very little time in the classroom to teach them, so extracurricular lessons are organized. Studying outside the classroom serves as the main tool of education, it increases the desire to know a lot. Studying outside the classroom is closely related to academic lessons, and it closely helps in the implementation of the goals and tasks envisaged in it.

For this, it is necessary to educate the culture of reading in students, to raise them from ordinary readers to the level of creative readers. It is necessary to approach each child individually, taking into account their personal interests, in order to arouse students' enthusiasm for books. Formation of children's ability to work on books is an important factor in raising reading culture in them.

Our people vividly reflected their joy, happiness or sadness in their songs. Fairy tales play a special role in developing children's imagination and fantasy. Each story that is told leaves a new impression on children. Children try to be like the heroes of fairy tales, they want to have magical things, or they dream of becoming a magician and having unlimited power like the hero. With the help of a fairy tale, they travel in the deserts of good and evil, in the hills and mountains. From such a period, they begin to understand what is good and what is bad. As children grow up, they tell stories to their younger ones, encourage them to be smart, restrained, to stop being stubborn and capricious. They also behave as small educators.

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